

A Correlation Study of Social Networking Addiction and Emotional Adjustment Among Adolescents

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Abstract

The present study is undertaken to assess the Social Networking addiction and Emotional Adjustment among adolescents. A total number of 60 students were the sample of the present study (30 Males, and 30 Females) selected randomly from Kolhapur city. “Social Networking Addiction” and “Emotional Adjustment Test” were used in the present study. Data was analysed by using Pearson product moment correlation (r), Mean, Standard Deviation and, ‘t’ test on SPSS. Result shows that there is significant relationship between social networking addiction and emotional adjustment, and there is significant difference between males and females on emotional adjustment among adolescents.

Keywords: Social networking, Addiction, Emotional adjustment

Introduction

Social Networking

Social networking refers to the use of online platforms and applications that enable individuals to connect, share information, and interact with others. It provides a virtual space for users to build and maintain relationships, exchange ideas, and share various forms of content, such as text, images, and videos. Popular social networking sites include Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and LinkedIn, each catering to different aspects of social interaction. These platforms have transformed how people communicate, collaborate, and express themselves in the digital age.

Definition: Social networking is the use of online platforms where people connect, share information, and interact with others, forming virtual communities and relationships.

Importance of Social Networking

1. **Communication and Connectivity:** Social networking facilitates instant communication, connecting people globally and fostering relationships with friends, family, and colleagues.
2. **Information Dissemination:** It serves as a rapid and widespread platform for sharing news, ideas, and knowledge, contributing to increased awareness and education.
3. **Professional Networking:** Platforms like LinkedIn provide opportunities for career advancement, job searching, and building professional connections.
4. **Community Building:** Social networks allow the formation of online communities based on shared interests, providing a sense of belonging and support.
5. **Business Opportunities:** It offers businesses a platform to reach a broader audience, engage with customers, and promote products or services, contributing to marketing and growth strategies.

Emotional Adjustment

Emotional adjustment refers to an individual's ability to adapt and cope with various emotional experiences, such as stress, frustration, or joy. It involves recognizing and managing one's emotions in a way that promotes mental well-being and effective functioning in different situations. Successful emotional adjustment enables individuals to navigate challenges, build resilience, and maintain a balanced emotional state.

Definition: Emotional adjustment is the capacity to cope with and manage one's emotions in response to life's challenges, fostering mental well-being and adaptability.

Importance of Emotional Adjustment

1. **Mental Well-being:** Emotional adjustment is crucial for maintaining mental health, promoting a positive emotional state, and reducing the risk of mental health issues such as anxiety and depression.
2. **Resilience:** Individuals with strong emotional adjustment skills can bounce back from adversity more effectively, developing resilience in the face of life's challenges.
3. **Healthy Relationships:** Effective emotional adjustment contributes to better interpersonal relationships by fostering empathy, understanding, and improved communication, creating a positive environment in personal and professional interactions.
4. **Stress Management:** Emotional adjustment equips individuals with tools to manage stress, preventing chronic stress from negatively impacting both mental and physical health.
5. **Adaptability:** The ability to adjust emotionally allows individuals to navigate and adapt to changing circumstances, promoting flexibility and a proactive approach to life's uncertainties.

Adolescent and Social Networking Addiction

Adolescent social networking addiction can impact mental health and well-being. Excessive use may lead to decreased face-to-face interactions, disrupted sleep, and feelings of isolation. Balancing online and offline activities is crucial for a healthy lifestyle.

Adolescent and Emotional Adjustment

Adolescent emotional adjustment involves navigating identity, relationships, and coping with challenges. Factors like family support, peer relationships, and coping skills play vital roles in shaping emotional well-being during this crucial developmental stage.

Relation Between Social Networking Addiction and Emotional Adjustment Among Adolescent

Research suggests a link between social networking addiction and poorer emotional adjustment among adolescents. Excessive online engagement may contribute to increased stress, anxiety, and difficulties in face-to-face interactions, impacting overall emotional well-being. It's essential to foster a balanced approach to technology use to support healthy emotional development.

Effects of Social Networking Addiction and Emotional Adjustment Among Adolescent

Social networking addiction in adolescents can negatively affect emotional adjustment. Excessive screen time may lead to social isolation, reduced face-to-face interactions, and comparison-driven stress. This can contribute to feelings of loneliness, anxiety, and hinder the development of essential emotional coping skills. Balancing online and offline activities is crucial for healthier emotional outcomes.

Significance of the study

Social networks are important because they allow people to develop relationships that might not be possible due to distances of place and time. They also help boost business productivity when used for public relations, marketing, and advertising purposes.

Emotional adjustment refers to one's acceptance of "self" or "self-concept." It is also explained as one's ability to be self-actualizing and fully functioning. The concept of a "fully functioning person is very closely related to emotional adjustment, as fully functioning describes a state when one is in optimum emotional health." Emotional adjustment is important for personality development and maintaining a physiologically and psychologically healthy life.

Problem Statement

To study social networking addiction and emotional adjustment among adolescents.

Objectives

1. To examine the correlation between social networking addiction and emotional adjustment among adolescents.
2. To examine the difference between male and female adolescents on emotional adjustments.
3. To examine the difference between male and female adolescents on social networking addiction.

Hypotheses

1. There will be significant association between social networking addiction and emotional adjustment among adolescents.
2. Male and female adolescents will significantly differ on their emotional adjustment.
3. Male and female adolescents will significantly differ on their social networking addiction.

Methodology

Participants: Through quota sampling method of data collection 60 adolescents (10-19) were divided into 2 groups, 30 males and 30 females.

Inclusion Criteria

- 1) Only adolescents' males and females are included.
- 2) Can read, write and speak Marathi and English.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Those who are not adolescents.

Variable

Independent Variable

Gender

Dependent Variable

1. Social Networking Addiction
2. Emotional Adjustment

Operational Definition

Social Networking Addiction: Social networking addiction refers to a compulsive and excessive use of social media platforms, leading to negative impacts on an individual's daily life, mental well-being, or relationships. It involves an inability to control the time spent on social networks, often resulting in neglect of other responsibilities and activities.

Emotional Adjustment: Emotional adjustment is the process through which individuals cope with and adapt to various emotional experiences, challenges, and changes in their lives. It involves the ability to regulate emotions, manage stress, and navigate different situations in a way that promotes psychological well-being and resilience.

Tools used in the study

1. Social networking scale [2020]

The scale is introduced by M.G. Shahnawaz and Usama Rehman. It contains 21 statements. Each statement has seven responses, that are, strongly agree, agree, neither agree nor disagree, somewhat agree, somewhat disagree, disagree, strongly disagree.

2. Emotional Adjustment [1993]

This scale is developed by Sinha and Singh. It contains 60 statements. Each statement has two responses, that were yes or no.

Procedure

Present study aims to understand the relationship between Social Networking Addiction and Emotional Adjustment among adolescents. The participants were adolescents, personal data sheet was provided. They were given 2 test to solve, stated in tools. Scoring was done manually of all 2 scales. Data was statistically analysed on Excel Data Analysis Tool pack.

Statistical analysis

Mean, SD, t-test and Pearson product moment correlation was used to statistically analyse the data.

Results

Table 1: Correlation Between Social Networking Addiction and Emotional Adjustment among adolescents.

Factor	N	Mean	SD	df	"r"
SNS	60	33.28	4.59	118	0.37*
EAS	60	58.23	23.35		

**Significant at 0.01 level, *Significant at 0.05 level- NS- Not Significant

Table 2: Mean, SD, value for type of gender difference on Social Networking among adolescents.

Factor	N	Mean	SD	df	"t"
Male	30	33.86	4.84	58	0.94 NS
Female	30	32.7	4.33		

**Significant at 0.01 level, *Significant at 0.05 level- NS- Not Significant

Table 3: Mean, SD, value for type of gender difference on Emotional Adjustment among adolescents.

Factor	N	Mean	SD	df	“t”
Male	30	62.13	24.26	58	6.62*
Female	30	24.26	19.91		

**Significant at 0.01 level, *Significant at 0.05 level- NS- Not Significant

Discussion and interpretation

Table 1 represents the correlation between social networking addiction and emotional adjustment among adolescents. Social networking addiction mean value is 33.28 and SD is 4.59 Emotional adjustment mean value is 58.23 and SD is 22.35. It shows that social networking addiction affects emotional adjustment.

Table 2. represents the difference between males and females on social networking addiction of adolescents. So, the mean score of males is 33.86 and SD is 4.84. Mean score of females is 32.7 and SD is 4.33. The “t” value which we get is 0.94. It shows that the significant difference is no found between male and female adolescents on social networking addiction.

Table 3 represents the difference between males and females on emotional adjustment within adolescents. So, the mean score for males is 62.13 and SD is 24.26. The mean score for females is 24.26 and SD is 19.91. The “t” value which we get is 6.62. It shows that the significant difference is found between male and female adolescents on emotional adjustment.

Conclusion

1. Correlation between social networking addiction and emotional adjustment among adolescents. Hence, it shows that social networking addiction affects emotional adjustment.
2. It represents that, the significant difference is no found between male and female adolescents on social networking addiction.
3. It represents that, the significant difference is found between male and female adolescents on emotional adjustment.

Limitation and Suggestion

1. Only psychological tests have been used for this research paper.
2. In this research paper, only 60 samples were taken for both the tests.
3. Adolescents from only one district were taken for this research paper.

Research Application

1. From the above test we come to know that male adolescents have higher social networking addiction in compare to female adolescents. So, we have to raise awareness among male adolescents.
2. From the above test we come to know that male adolescents have higher emotional adjustment in compare to female adolescents. So, we have to raise awareness among male adolescents.

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